

On model selection of nonparametric regression models with autoregressive and moving average errors

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Abstract

We are interested in model selection of nonparametric regression model with correlated random errors under a random design setup, where the random errors are assumed to follow an autoregressive and moving average (ARMA) process and the covariates can also be serially correlated. We proposed a spline-based method to estimate the mean function and the parameters of the ARMA process jointly based on a least squares method. The asymptotic properties of the method have been proven, and extensive simulation studies have shown the superior performance of least square method compared to the previous two-step sequential method. Along these lines, we propose utilizing BIC to assist in model selection. The consistency property of BIC for model selection is established. Simulation studies are performed to assess the finite performance of BIC in model selection.

1 Introduction

The model of interest is defined as

$$Y_t = g_0(X_t) + \epsilon_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, n, \quad (1)$$

where $g_0(\cdot)$ is an unknown smooth regression function, and ϵ_t follows an ARMA(p_0, q_0) process, that is

$$\epsilon_t - \sum_{i=1}^{p_0} \phi_{i*} \epsilon_{t-i} = \zeta_t + \sum_{j=1}^{q_0} \theta_{j*} \zeta_{t-j}, \quad (2)$$

for which the true ARMA orders and true ARMA parameters are respectively denoted as (p_0, q_0) and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* = (\boldsymbol{\phi}_*^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}_*^\top)^\top = (\phi_{1*}, \dots, \phi_{p_0*}, \theta_{1*}, \dots, \theta_{q_0*})^\top$. Kernel methods and spline approximations are the primary approaches in nonparametric regression. Our focus is on a spline-based method for model estimation. The literature on kernel regression for

estimating model (1) includes [Truong \(1991\)](#); [Hall and Keilegom \(2003\)](#); [Liang and Jing \(2009\)](#); [Lee et al. \(2010\)](#), among others. Nonetheless, due to computational simplicity, the spline approximation method also attracts substantial interest (see, e.g., [Shao and Yang, 2017](#); [Zheng et al., 2024](#)).

Unlike the previous spline-based method, which estimates the smooth function $g_0(\cdot)$ and the ARMA parameters α_* sequentially in two steps (the two-step approach), [Zheng et al. \(2024\)](#) proposed a one-step method to estimate the smooth function and the parameters of the ARMA process jointly based on least squares. The one-step method allows spline approximations and ARMA models to compete on an equal basis on the same stage to minimize sum of squared errors, rather than relegating ARMA models to a second place. The asymptotic properties of the one-step approach were established under a random design setup. Extensive simulation studies demonstrated that the one-step method outperforms the earlier two-step method. However, the asymptotic results developed in [Zheng et al. \(2024\)](#) are based on the condition that the ARMA order (p_0, q_0) are known a priori, and the problem of ARMA order selection (estimation) was left unaddressed.

This project will continue in the same direction as our previous efforts ([Zheng et al., 2024](#)). We propose utilizing BIC to assist in ARMA order selection.

2 BIC for ARMA order selection

We first introduce the one-step method for estimating (1). Let $\boldsymbol{\xi} = (\boldsymbol{\beta}^\top, \boldsymbol{\phi}^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top)^\top$ be a parameter vector, comprising coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}^\top$ for $\mathbf{B}_n(u) = (B_1(u), \dots, B_J(u))^\top$, a set of spline basis functions, and ARMA parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\boldsymbol{\phi}^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top)^\top$ of an ARMA(p, q) model. Define the estimates of ϵ_t by

$$\epsilon_t(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t \leq 0, \\ Y_t - \boldsymbol{\beta}^\top \mathbf{W}_t, & \text{if } t > 0, \end{cases}$$

where \mathbf{W}_t is the design matrix induced by $\mathbf{B}_n(u)$, and then for $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_p, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_q)^\top$ calculate the estimates of ζ_t by

$$\zeta_t(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \epsilon_t(\boldsymbol{\beta})) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t \leq 0, \\ \epsilon_t(\boldsymbol{\beta}) - \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \epsilon_{t-i}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) - \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j \zeta_{t-j}(\boldsymbol{\xi}), & \text{if } t > 0. \end{cases}$$

We obtain $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top, \hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}^\top, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^\top)^\top$, the least squares estimator of $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, by minimizing $\mathcal{L}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{t=1}^n \zeta_t^2(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \epsilon_t(\boldsymbol{\beta}))/n$. In fact, $\mathcal{L}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ can also be written as $\sum_{t=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=0}^{t-1} \pi_j \epsilon_{t-j}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \right)^2 / n$, with the coefficients π_j obtained from the power series expansion

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \pi_j z^j = \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}(z)}{\boldsymbol{\theta}(z)} = \frac{1 - \phi_1 z - \dots - \phi_p z^p}{1 + \theta_1 z + \dots + \theta_q z^q},$$

for AR polynomial $\boldsymbol{\phi}(z) = 1 - \phi_1 z - \dots - \phi_p z^p$ and MA polynomial $\boldsymbol{\theta}(z) = 1 + \theta_1 z + \dots + \theta_q z^q$. We denote the AR polynomial and the MA polynomial for the true ARMA parameters by

$\phi_*(z)$ and $\theta_*(z)$.

To distinguish least squares estimations with different ARMA orders, we explicitly introduce (p, q) into the picture, i.e. using $\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\alpha}, p, q)$ to denote the optimal least squares function value for orders (p, q) , where $\hat{\beta}$ and $\hat{\alpha}$ denote the related least squares estimates for ARMA parameters,

$$\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\alpha}, p, q) = \sum_{t=1}^n \zeta_t^2(\hat{\alpha}, \epsilon_t(\hat{\beta}))/n.$$

Subsequently, we define

$$BIC(p, q) = \log(\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\beta}, \hat{\alpha}, p, q)) + \frac{p+q}{n} \log(n).$$

The BIC orders estimator, denoted as (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) , is obtained as the minimizer of BIC,

$$(\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) = \arg \min_{(p, q)} BIC(p, q).$$

To study the properties of (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) , the regularity conditions of [Zheng et al. \(2024\)](#) are inherited.

- (C1) $g_0(\cdot) \in \mathcal{C}_D^{(\alpha)}(\mathcal{X})$, where $\mathcal{C}_D^{(\alpha)}(\mathcal{X})$ is the collection of the continuous functions $g : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on a bounded set $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}$ with the α th derivative $\|g^{(\alpha)}\|_\infty \leq D$, for some integer $\alpha \geq 2$ and $D > 0$. Without loss of generality, we assume $\mathcal{X} = [0, 1]$.
- (C2) The polynomials $\phi_*(z)$ and $\theta_*(z)$ have no common roots, and their roots lie outside the unit circle in the complex plane.
- (C3) $\{\zeta_t\}_{t=1}^n$ and $\{X_t\}_{t=1}^n$ are independent. ζ_t 's are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) with $E[\zeta_t] = 0$ and $E[\zeta_t^2] = \sigma^2$. In addition, ζ_t satisfies the Bernstein's condition, that is, $E[|\zeta_t|^k] \leq k! C_B^k / 2$, for some large $C_B > 0$ and $k \geq 1$.
- (C4) $\{X_t\}$ is a strictly stationary sequence of absolutely continuous random variables and $\{X_t\}$ is β -mixing with coefficients $\beta(k) \leq 2 \exp(-d_1 k^{\gamma_1})$ for any positive k , where $d_1, \gamma_1 > 0$. Let

$$\mathbf{\Gamma} = E \left[\frac{\phi_*(B)}{\theta_*(B)} \mathbf{W}_t \left(\frac{\phi_*(B)}{\theta_*(B)} \mathbf{W}_t \right)^\top \right].$$

The smallest eigenvalue of $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ is bounded below by $\lambda_{\min} J^{-1}$, for some constant $\lambda_{\min} > 0$.

Based on C1)–(C4), we are able to show that the proposed BIC order selector is consistent for preventing ARMA model overfitting. More specifically, the following theorem is in order.

Theorem 1 *Suppose Conditions (C1)–(C4) hold and $J \sim n^{1/(2\alpha+1)}$, then*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(BIC(p, q) - BIC(p_0, q_0) > 0) = 1, \text{ for } p > p_0 \text{ and } q > q_0.$$

Remark 2.1 *It should be noted that at this time we are not able to address the other half of the puzzle, i.e., the proposed BIC order estimator is consistent for preventing ARMA model underfitting*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(BIC(p, q) - BIC(p_0, q_0) > 0) = 1, \text{ for } p < p_0 \text{ or } q < q_0.$$

3 Simulation studies

The initial values of the ARMA parameters for the optimization process are generated by random numbers over $[0, 1]$, and all parameters for the basis functions are set to be one. The numerical optimization of the loss function runs smoothly and efficiently. An implementation of the proposed method by R consistently yields model estimates that are close to the true ARMA parameters across repeated tests, in strong agreement with Theorem 2 of Zheng et al. (2024). For further details of the numerical implementation of the proposed one-step method, interested readers are invited to visit <https://github.com/cui-yun-wei/trend-mod> to play with the code.

Comprehensive evaluations of (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) were conducted based on simulation studies. The covariate variable X_t 's were generated from AR(1) process first and then rescaled within $\mathcal{X} = [0, 1]$. Three smooth functions, with different shapes and curvatures, were used for $g_0(X_t)$.

$$\begin{cases} f_1(X_t) = 1 - 6X_t + 36X_t^2 - 53X_t^3 + 22X_t^5; \\ f_2(X_t) = \sin(2\pi X_t) + 2X_t^2; \\ f_3(X_t) = \arctan(X_t/2 - 1/4) - X_t^2/3. \end{cases}$$

Samples of (1), $\{Y_t\}$, were simulated with random errors ϵ_t following various *AR*, *MA*, and *ARMA* models. The length of the observations were chosen as $n = 200$, $n = 500$, and $n = 1000$. By allowing p and q to vary from 0 to 3, a total of 16 order settings can be generated. Excluding the trivial case where $p = 0$ and $q = 0$, we have 15 options for (p, q) . For each set of selected smooth function $g_0(\cdot)$, ARMA model, and sample path length n , $\{Y_t\}_{t=1}^n$ were generated first, and then the $BIC(p, q)$ values were computed for the 15 different order settings, from which the minimizer (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) was determined.

The model simulation and BIC order estimation process were repeated 100 times for each model setting. Summary tables of the simulations were attached in the Appendix B. In each table, the proportion of correctly selected models by BIC order selector was reported. As we expected, the performance of the model selector was affected by the model specifications, in terms of smooth function $g_0(\cdot)$ and ARMA model. Despite the differences in modeling settings, it is evident that the success rate increases with sample path length n , which strongly attests the validity of Theorem 1. The BIC order selector demonstrated consistency property, as in most cases it successfully navigated through the mists of underfitted or overfitted models to identify the correct model order.

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Appendix A

Let $\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_*) = \sum_{t=1}^n \zeta_t^2(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_*, \epsilon_t(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}))/n$ and $\mathcal{L}_n = \sum_{t=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=0}^{t-1} \pi_{j*} \epsilon_{t-j} \right)^2 / n$ where π_{j*} 's are given by the power series expansion of $\boldsymbol{\phi}_*(z)/\boldsymbol{\theta}_*(z)$ for the true parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* = (\boldsymbol{\phi}_*^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}_*^\top)^\top$. It is known that \mathcal{L}_n is a consistent estimator of σ^2 , the variance of the innovations, i.e., $\mathcal{L}_n - \sigma^2 = o_p(1)$ (cf. Fuller, 1996).

Proof of Theorem 1: Using a second-order Taylor's expansion of $\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_*)$

$$\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_*) = \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0) + (\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* - \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})^\top \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})}{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}} + \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* - \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})^\top \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha} \partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}^\top} (\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* - \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})$$

where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = (1-t)\boldsymbol{\alpha}_* + t\hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$, for $t \in [0, 1]$. The gradient term is zero, since $(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^\top, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}^\top)^\top$ is a local minimizer. Invoking Theorem 1 in Zheng et al. (2024) we can show $\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_*) - \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0) = o_p(1)$

$$\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0) - \mathcal{L}_n = o_p(1).$$

In the case of overfitting, $p > p_0$ or $q > q_0$, since $(\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{p_0})^\top$ can be written as $(\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{p_0}, 0, \dots, 0)$ with $p - p_0$ zeros, and $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{q_0})^\top$ can be written as $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{q_0}, 0, \dots, 0)$ with $q - q_0$ zeros, it still holds true $\mathcal{L}_n(p, q) - \mathcal{L}_n = o_p(1) = o_p(1)$, even when the incorrect order is adopted. Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BIC}(p, q) - \text{BIC}(p_0, q_0) &= \log \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p, q)}{\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0)} \right) + \frac{p + q - p_0 - q_0}{n} \log(n) \\ &= \log \left(1 + \frac{\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p, q) - \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0)}{\mathcal{L}_n(p_0, q_0)} \right) + \frac{p + q - p_0 - q_0}{n} \log(n) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p, q) - \mathcal{L}_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}, p_0, q_0)}{\sigma^2} (1 + o_p(1)) + \frac{p + q - p_0 - q_0}{n} \log(n) \\ &= o_p(1) + \frac{p + q - p_* - q_*}{n} \log(n). \end{aligned}$$

Due to $p + q - p_* - q_* > 0$ for the overfitting case,

$$P(\text{BIC}(p, q) - \text{BIC}(p_0, q_0) > 0) \rightarrow 1.$$

□

Appendix B

Table 1: Proportion of AR(2) models correctly selected by BIC, when X_t 's are serially correlated and satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1, and innovations ζ_t 's have a t distribution with degrees of freedom ν .

$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (-0.8, -0.5) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.87	0.95	0.99	0.9	0.94	0.99	0.87	0.97	0.99
$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (-0.5, -0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.15	0.32	0.67	0.18	0.3	0.65	0.11	0.3	0.65
$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (-0.3, -0.4) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.76	0.92	0.97	0.76	0.94	0.99	0.73	0.92	0.98
$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (0.5, 0.1) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.06	0.1	0.46	0.1	0.15	0.41	0.02	0.24	0.37
$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (0.6, 0.3) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.68	0.84	0.92	0.62	0.84	0.92	0.63	0.82	0.92
$(\phi_1, \phi_2) = (0.3, 0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.42	0.76	0.89	0.31	0.65	0.88	0.43	0.65	0.9

Table 2: Proportion of MA(2) models correctly selected by BIC, when X_t 's are serially correlated and satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1, and innovations ζ_t 's have a t distribution with degrees of freedom ν .

$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (-0.6, -0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.42	0.51	0.77	0.52	0.64	0.81	0.5	0.5	0.8
$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (-0.5, -0.3) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.74	0.75	0.92	0.72	0.74	0.96	0.68	0.79	0.96
$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (-0.3, -0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.47	0.64	0.91	0.56	0.68	0.92	0.44	0.85	0.83
$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (0.4, 0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.12	0.24	0.67	0.13	0.33	0.57	0.13	0.25	0.59
$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (0.5, 0.3) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.47	0.71	0.95	0.51	0.78	0.97	0.48	0.84	0.97
$(\theta_1, \theta_2) = (0.8, 0.1) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.06	0.16	0.44	0.08	0.22	0.39	0.09	0.18	0.36

Table 3: Proportion of ARMA(1,1) models correctly selected by BIC, when X_t 's are serially correlated and satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1, and innovations ζ_t 's have a t distribution with degrees of freedom ν .

$(\phi, \theta) = (0.6, 0.3) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.58	0.75	0.85	0.53	0.67	0.92	0.53	0.72	0.89
$(\phi, \theta) = (-0.8, -0.8) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.95	0.95	0.99	0.91	0.99	0.98	0.91	0.98	0.97
$(\phi, \theta) = (-0.8, -0.2) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.38	0.6	0.75	0.45	0.65	0.73	0.32	0.65	0.75
$(\phi, \theta) = (-0.6, -0.6) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.88	0.99	0.99	0.95	0.99	0.96	0.86	0.95	0.99
$(\phi, \theta) = (-0.8, 0.6) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.35	0.86	0.92	0.44	0.85	0.93	0.37	0.76	0.92
$(\phi, \theta) = (0.8, 0.8) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.93	0.99	0.98	0.92	0.99	0.99	0.95	0.97	1
$(\phi, \theta) = (0.8, 0.6) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.94	0.99	1	0.91	0.97	0.99	0.91	0.99	0.99
$(\phi, \theta) = (0.6, 0.6) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.86	0.95	0.99	0.91	0.94	0.99	0.87	0.96	0.99
$(\phi, \theta) = (0.8, -0.6) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.41	0.78	0.98	0.39	0.82	0.95	0.29	0.74	0.97

Table 4: Proportion of AR(1) models correctly selected by BIC, when X_t 's are serially correlated and satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1, and innovations ζ_t 's have a t distribution with degrees of freedom ν .

$\phi = -0.8 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.91	0.96	0.99	0.91	0.96	0.99	0.88	0.95	0.99
$\phi_1 = -0.5 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.88	0.97	0.96	0.83	0.94	0.98	0.85	0.96	0.96
$\phi = -0.3 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.51	0.72	0.87	0.61	0.8	0.93	0.69	0.79	0.89
$\phi = 0.2 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.57	0.65	0.81	0.52	0.55	0.66	0.5	0.57	0.74
$\phi = 0.6 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.92	0.94	0.97	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.92	0.98	0.99
$\phi = 0.8 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.92	0.96	0.98	0.87	0.94	1	0.94	0.96	0.99

Table 5: Proportion of MA(1) models correctly selected by BIC, when X_t 's are serially correlated and satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1, and innovations ζ_t 's have a t distribution with degrees of freedom ν .

$\theta = -0.8 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.91	0.93	0.99	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.91	0.99	0.99
$\theta = -0.6 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.85	0.96	0.97	0.77	0.94	0.97	0.87	0.96	0.97
$\theta = -0.3 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.73	0.85	0.91	0.79	0.9	0.9	0.66	0.87	0.86
$\theta = 0.2 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.6	0.63	0.66	0.54	0.7	0.77	0.64	0.69	0.73
$\theta = 0.7 \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.9	0.98	0.97	0.85	0.98	0.98	0.86	0.92	0.97
$(\theta) = (0.5) \quad \nu = 3$									
g_0	$f_1(X_t)$			$f_2(X_t)$			$f_3(X_t)$		
n	200	500	1000	200	500	1000	200	500	1000
	0.89	0.95	0.98	0.95	0.94	0.98	0.9	0.97	0.99